

The holy Kjeld of Viborg (younger text)

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The holy Kjeld was a dean from Viborg diocese. He died on 27. September 1150 and with papal permission he was later canonized by archbishop Absalon of Denmark in 1188. Two hagiographic texts are known about the holy Kjeld of Viborg, an older one and a younger one, although the younger one has gone widely unnoticed and very little has been written about it. A main reason that it has been largely forgotten is probably the fact that it was left out of both primary source editions of Danish medieval hagiography, as neither M. Cl. Gertz (*Vitae Sanctorum Danorum*) nor Hans Olrik (*Danske Helgeners Levned*) included it in their books. As to why these choices were made, one can only speculate. It may have been simply overlooked, but more likely it may have been a conscious choice made because of doubt related to its actual age and origin. At their time, this source had been published only in a somewhat obsolete latin edition from the 1700s. Shortly after their time, however, a posthumous article by a young Danish historian, Thomas B. Bang, who had by then already died from the Spanish flu, shed some much needed new light on the younger text when he republished the source in a Danish local historical journal. His new source edition differed from the older edition in two ways primarily. First of all, he published it in Danish. This actually seems to have been the language that the source had been written in originally, but Jacob Langebek who had published it in the 1700s had made the odd choice of translating it from Danish into latin before he published it. Just as importantly, Bang also succeeded in shedding some much needed new light on the source. What the article by Thomas B. Bang did not succeed in doing, though, was making the source known to a larger audience. As it had by now already been left out of the books by Gertz and Olrik and the new article by Thomas B. Bang also went largely unnoticed, fact still is that only very little has been written about this text since Bang's time. It was mentioned (although not republished) in a later source edition of the older texts about St. Kjeld by Henning Høirup and O.F. Stjernfeldt, but apart from that, this appears to be the very first article about the younger text since Thomas B. Bang's time. The older text on St. Kjeld and the younger text about St. Kjeld, respectively, are quite different not only in dating and in their individual background of creation, but also stylistically. The younger text about the holy Kjeld of Viborg does not follow the normal somewhat stricter structure of hagiography, but is instead a structurally loose collection of information of his life and kin put together with miracle stories also connected to Kjeld's own lifetime. Structurally the text thus bears much more resemblance to the younger text about the holy Niels than it does to the older and structurally stricter generations of Danish hagiography. Together with the text about the holy Anders and also with the younger text about the holy Niels, this younger text about the holy Kjeld paints the picture of an existing, although previously unnoticed, younger generation of late medieval Danish hagiography which differed from the older generation of Danish hagiography by being much more loose structurally. While the older generations of Danish hagiography can be viewed as being hagiography in the much more classic sense of the term, this younger generation of Danish hagiography from the late medieval period perhaps were not hagiography in the stricter sense of that term as much as they were simply loose collections of material gathered on the saint in question. This younger generation of Danish hagiography also differed from the older generation of Danish hagiographical texts in another way. While the older generations of texts generally put much weight on documentation by talking to eye witnesses etc., the younger generation of texts did not have that opportunity as all eye witnesses were by now dead long ago. Thus instead they relied on stories and information circulating orally not only amongst the people, but also amongst the clerics themselves in the milieu where it was written down. The texts also gathered written information where they could (as with the now lost book in Danish referred to by the younger Niels text), and they then mixed it all together into a miscellaneous collection of material on the

saint in question. Just like the younger text about the holy Niels, the younger text about St. Kjeld is thus not a classic hagiographic text as much as it is a composite collection of anecdotes and miracle stories deemed worthy of remembrance by the author. Reviewing the text more closely than has been done in the past, it becomes clear that the text published by Bang actually differs slightly from the text that Langebek translated into Latin and published in the 1700s. This can be proven easiest by mentioning a few examples of this (amongst more such differences of detail): The Langebek version mentions the later burial in the cathedral of the Danish king Svend III Grathe (murdered 1157). The Bang edition omits this completely, but includes instead a faulty late medieval tradition that Kjeld had been elected bishop of Viborg (cf. below). The two texts both mention Kjeld's father, but by two different first names. Langebek and Bang therefore must have used different manuscript versions of the text, although the two manuscript versions must have been closely related and stemming from the same overall textual tradition. Possibly both manuscripts consist of partial copies and extracts from a larger, now lost medieval manuscript. This, however, would not necessarily explain the different first name by which Kjeld's father is referred to in the two editions. Thus another perhaps more likely possibility is that there may have existed more than one medieval manuscript version of this text and that the Langebek edition and the Bang edition, respectively, derives from different medieval manuscripts. A main reason that both Gertz and Olrik omitted the text from their books probably is that they doubted whether the text was actually medieval at all. As these two publishers knew only the Langebek edition, this is understandable. Langebek himself stated that he found the manuscript that he used amongst the papers of Henrik Gerner (bishop of Viborg 1693-1700), and this Langebek edition of the text remains extremely hazy on when the text was actually dated. The two manuscripts of the text that later Bang found and used for his article, however, contains a rather strange introduction text which sheds new light on the dating of the text and proves its medieval origins. This information was unbeknownst to Gertz and Olrik as the two manuscripts used by Bang had not yet been found when they published their books. The true nature of the strange introduction is revealed only when understood that it consists of notes written on more than one occasion by three generations of different owners and copyists. The oldest generation of owner who made such a note was nobleman Tyge Krabbe (d. 1541) who luckily provides us with the year that he made his copy by saying that he made his copy in the year 1524. Naturally this means that the text must be older than that and thus it is now already proven that the text was really written in the middle ages. The only question remaining thus is when exactly it was written. The second generation of owner was Anne Krabbe, the daughter of Tyge Krabbe's son. Her introductory note must have been written sometime around 1590, as she says in it (in Danish): "this is written a hundred years ago at anno 1490". Later on Høirup and Stjernfelt therefore referred to 1490 as the dating of the text, when they mentioned the text in their book. The question is whether this exact year can be trusted. On the one hand Anne Krabbe remains silent on where she had this piece of information from. Thus it could potentially be a simple guess on her behalf. On the other hand, being such an exact dating, 1490 seems a slightly strange year to simply invent out of the blue. Thus it could be suspected that she may have either seen that year in the lost medieval manuscript that was copied or at least either have heard or seen it referred to from that manuscript. Moreover, although that exact year is impossible to prove, it agrees quite well with other overall circumstances: First of all, the note by Tyge Krabbe proved that the text was definitely written at least a number of years before 1524. As above, stylistically the text also fits rather well into the late medieval type of hagiographical texts that can be identified in Denmark. Thirdly, it is of importance that the Bang edition of the text includes a faulty late medieval tradition that Kjeld was elected bishop of Viborg even though it is known with certainty from contemporary sources (including the older hagiographical text about Kjeld) that this was actually never the case. This tradition that he was actually elected bishop seems to have arisen because later traditions had him confused with another Viborg bishop called Eskil. This confusion is understood when looking at two details from the older text about St. Kjeld. The first detail is the fact that the older text describes how Kjeld strived for martyrdom and wanted to travel to preach for the heathen people called the Vends, but apparently ended up simply returning home after meeting up with the Pope in Rome. The second detail regards the abovementioned bishop Eskil of Viborg. The older text describes how it was bishop Eskil of Viborg who ordained Kjeld as a priest, but also how this very same bishop Eskil was later murdered by enemies of Christ who attacked him at the altar in the middle of church service. This murder took place in 1132 in the still preserved Asmild monastery church during a civil war and was carried

out by the men of king Erik II Emune of Denmark. The reason for the murder probably being that Eskil most likely supported the reigning king Niels who was Erik Emune's enemy. These two details combined, Kjeld's ambitions of martyrdom, and the murder of bishop Eskil were blended together later on and thus arose a confusing and faulty late medieval tradition that Kjeld was bishop of Viborg and a martyr saint. The faulty episcopal tradition of Kjeld seems to appear for the first time in a document from 1346 confirming the privileges of the holy chapter in Viborg. By around 1400 this faulty tradition apparently had Kjeld equipped with full-blown martyrdom as he is pictured with a palm branch on the seal of Lage Glob, bishop of Viborg 1396-1429. This faulty tradition is confirmed also by other late medieval sources. Although not mentioning martyrdom, it must be this faulty late medieval episcopal tradition that the younger text derives from when it mentions that Kjeld was elected bishop. Conclusively, although 1490 remains unconfirmed as the exact year of dating of the younger text, it is probably quite likely as other circumstances prove that the text must have been written definitely before 1524 and likely after c. 1346. As for the text itself, the Langebek edition and the Bang edition both follow the same overall structure by starting out with describing both Kjeld himself, his accomplishments and also his family and then continuing on by telling the same two miracle stories from his lifetime. As above, though, some of the details in terms of exact content differ somewhat when looking closely at the two text editions. The two miracle stories seem to have been based on oral stories circulating about Kjeld in late medieval Viborg and especially perhaps in the holy chapter there. What sources exactly that their more biographical introduction content was based on is harder to say. Question is whether this was also just based on oral traditions or whether this introductory part could have been partially based on written source material (just like the biographical content in the younger Niels text clearly was). The preserved source material, however, leave this question open for debate. Clearly, however, the miracle story with him reading the Bible in darkness echoes a passage within the older text on St. Kjeld.

Date Range: 1346 CE - 1524 CE

Region: Diocese of Viborg

Region tags: Denmark

Rough map of the diocese of Viborg, medieval Denmark

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Jakob Langebek (P.F. Suhm, ed.): *Scriptores Rerum Danicarum medii ævi*, tomus IV, 1776
- Source 2: Thomas B. Bang: "En Beretning fra Viborg om St. Kjeld", [in]: *Samlinger til Jydsk Historie og Topografi*, 4. series, IV. volume, København 1922-1924

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: not published outside of the editions mentioned above

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: not published outside of the editions mentioned above

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked
– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper
– *Specify*: The original manuscript is not preserved. Although now preserved only in a copies, being a late medieval text it could actually have been written on paper also originally. This is unlike the older hagiographical texts from earlier medieval Denmark as these must have been written on parchment originally. texts

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– *Other [specify]*: This is unknown as it is uncertain whether the original version was written on paper or parchment.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– *Other [specify]*: The original manuscript is not preserved.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb
– Field doesn't know

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– Yes

Notes: This is possible, cf. note below.

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: This is possible, cf. note below.

↳ Specify

– Specify: It seems that the was written probably by a canon at the holy chapter of Viborg diocese. It was thus probably kept either in or in connection to Viborg cathedral.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is possible if it was stored in Viborg cathedral. There could have been mural paintings there.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: as above

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: The answer is perhaps both yes and no at the same time. The writer was not necessarily paid for

his work, but the text seems to have been written by a canon of the holy chapter and this institution gained from the saint's cult financially.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The answer is perhaps both yes and no at the same time. The older text was probably considered to be the official saint's vita, but this text to some extent must have reflected the beliefs connected to his his saint's cult as it was practised in late medieval Denmark.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: It seems to have been written in Danish originally.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: Depends on the definition. The holy chapter naturally gained new members as time went by.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: The answer is perhaps both yes and no at the same time. The older text was probably considered to be the official saint's vita, but this text to some extent must have reflected the beliefs connected to his his saint's cult as this was practised in late medieval Denmark and the text thus could also reflect the beliefs embedded in the rituals connected to his saint's cult.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: Images picturing St. Kjeld are preserved, but they were probably not connected to this text.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Cf. introduction text

Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– No

Notes: The answer is probably yes and no at the same time. It was probably the older text which was mainly viewed as the official text about his life, but there is no sign of any such distinguishing between the different versions of the younger text.

Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Cultural with religious implications?

– No

Behavioral literature?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that hagiography can be viewed as that

Other

–Other [specify]: hagiography

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?

(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: none of the above

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Notes: It speaks of his burial in Viborg cathedral in a chapel where only he was buried.

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: none

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Notes: The text is connected to his saint's cult and thus also to the miracle cult at his burial place in Viborg cathedral.

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: noe of the above

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– No

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

Notes: It speaks of Kjeld's noble birth and familial background.

- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - No
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - No
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
 - No
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
 - No
- ↳ Other important virtues
 - No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: But Kjeld's clerical life did.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer,

etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: One of the miracle stories in the text speaks of how he read in the Bible at matutin in the winter when the light that he used suddenly went out, but he was able to continue reading anyway as if he had still held the light in his hand.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that the text seems to have been based on oral stories told about Kjeld.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– No

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Notes: But the text ascribes it to him having had the southern tower on Viborg cathedral built.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: The production of the text seems to have been connected to the holy chapter at Viborg cathedral. An anonymous canon there seems to have written down some miracle stories told orally.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The production of the text seems to have been connected to the holy chapter at Viborg cathedral.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: none of the above

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– No

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: The text attributes the building of the southern tower of Viborg cathedral to Kjeld

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: But one of the miracle stories in the text speaks of Kjeld turning water from a spring into wine.

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